

AN INNOVATIVE FEATURE OF INTUITIVE KNOWLEDGE

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Abstract. Intuition has many forms: intuition-judgment, statement (judgment of voluntary, intuitive truth), intuition - assumption, anticipation (heuristic intuition, assumption, expectation, expectation), and insight - understanding (from experience). Intuitive judgment is a direct definition of reality that does not need proof. In mathematics, intuitive judgment is an axiom. The intuitive assumption is the subject of theoretical (mathematical, logical) or experimental proof. In mathematics, intuition-anticipation is a theorem.

Logic and intuition based on human knowledge. on the basis of the development of science, art and religions, they are closely related. The difference is that while science interprets explanations using logical observations based on physical scientific laws, art and religion perceive concepts with intuition, and in the explanation it is based on logic.

Logic is a combination of classical (formal) logic that uses a set of rules, laws, and "non-classical logic" (rules valid for specific situations). Classical logic uses the "excluded third law" as a basic rule, meaning that every statement is true or false. In this context, the classical physics of this type of logic forms the basis of scientific analysis. However, explaining the electron motion requires, for example, the use of an additional "opportunity" (i.e., the proposition coincides with the specified probability level). Formal logic is historically invariant and leads to conclusions that are easily observed in any religion. In classical science (mainly physics), this approach allows new (additional) laws (rules) to be repealed without any effect on the old ones.

Keywords: intuition, scientific knowledge, brain, the function brain, problem and to solve it.

Аннотация. Интуиция имеет много форм: интуиция-суждение, утверждение (суждение о добровольной, интуитивной истине), интуиция - предположение, предвосхищение (эвристическая интуиция, предположение, ожидание, чаяния) и инсайт - понимание (из опыта). Интуитивное суждение - это прямое определение реальности, которое не нуждается в доказательствах. В математике интуитивное суждение является аксиомой. Интуитивное предположение является предметом теоретического (математического, логического) или экспериментального доказательства. В математике интуиция-предвосхищение - это теорема.

Логика и интуиция основаны на человеческих знаниях. на основе развития науки, искусства и религий они тесно связаны. Разница в том, что в то время как наука интерпретирует объяснения, используя логические наблюдения, основанные на физических научных законах, искусство и религия воспринимают концепции интуитивно, и в объяснении они основаны на логике.

Логика - это сочетание классической (формальной) логики, использующей набор правил, закономерностей и "неклассической логики" (правил, применимых к конкретным ситуациям). Классическая логика использует "закон исключенного третьего" в качестве основного правила, означающего, что каждое утверждение истинно или ложно. В этом контексте классическая физика этого типа логики составляет основу научного анализа. Однако объяснение движения электрона требует, например, использования дополнительной "возможности" (т.е., чтобы предположение совпадало с заданным

уровнем вероятности). Формальная логика исторически инвариантна и приводит к выводам, которые легко прослеживаются в любой религии. В классической науке (в основном в физике) этот подход позволяет отменять новые (дополнительные) законы (правила) без какого-либо влияния на старые.

Ключевые слова: интуиция, научное знание, мозг, функция мозга, проблема и способ ее решения.

Annotatsiya. Intuitsiya ko'p shakllarga ega: sezgi-hukm, bayonot (ixtiyoriy, intuitiv haqiqat to'g'risida hukm), sezgi - taxmin, kutish (evristik sezgi, taxmin, kutish, intilishlar) va tushuncha - tushunish (tajribadan). Intuitiv hukm-bu dalillarga muhtoj bo'lmagan haqiqatning to'g'ridan-to'g'ri ta'rifi. Matematikada intuitiv hukm aksioma hisoblanadi. Intuitiv taxmin nazariy (matematik, mantiqiy) yoki eksperimental dalillarning mavzusidir. Matematikada sezgi-kutish-bu teorema.

Mantiq va intuitsiya inson bilimlariga asoslanadi. ilm-fan, san'at va dinlarning rivojlanishi asosida ular bir-biri bilan chambarchas bog'liqdir. Farqi shundaki, fan fizik ilmiy qonunlarga asoslangan mantiqiy kuzatishlar yordamida tushuntirishlarni talqin qilsa-da, san'at va din tushunchalarni intuitiv ravishda qabul qiladi va tushuntirishda ular mantiqqa asoslanadi.

Mantiq-bu qoidalar, naqshlar va "klassik bo'lmagan mantiq" (muayyan vaziyatlarga tegishli qoidalar) to'plamidan foydalangan holda klassik (rasmiy) mantiqning kombinatsiyasi. Klassik mantiq" chiqarib tashlangan uchinchi qonun " dan asosiy qoida sifatida foydalanadi, ya'ni har bir bayonot to'g'ri yoki noto'g'ri. Shu nuqtai nazardan, ushbu turdagi mantiqning klassik fizikasi ilmiy tahlilning asosini tashkil etadi. Biroq, elektron harakatini tushuntirish, masalan, qo'shimcha "imkoniyat" dan foydalanishni talab qiladi (ya'ni taxmin berilgan ehtimollik darajasiga to'g'ri kelishi uchun). Rasmiy mantiq tarixiy jihatdan o'zgarmas bo'lib, har qanday dinda osongina kuzatilishi mumkin bo'lgan xulosalarga olib keladi. Klassik fanda (asosan fizikada) bu yondashuv eski qonunlarga hech qanday ta'sir ko'rsatmasdan yangi (qo'shimcha) qonunlarni (qoidalarni) bekor qilishga imkon beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: intuitsiya, ilmiy bilim, miya, funktsiya miya, muammo va uni hal qilish.

Introduction. According to rational thinking, it is recognized that scientific knowledge is a source of knowledge and the criterion of its reliability can only be achieved with the help of reason. "Rationalism - (from Latin rationalis - reason, the ratio of reasonable forces) is a philosophical direction that considers the knowledge of reason and the fact that people are the basis of morality."Rationalism emerged as an alternative to the interpretation of mathematical truths and properties of medicine. Its representatives in the 17th century were R. Descartes, B. Spinoza, G. Leibnis, representatives of the 18th century - I. Kant, I. Fixte, Schelling, V.F.Hegel. At the moment, rationalism is one of the philosophical origins of representatives of the Enlightenment ideology. The first historical form of rationalism was the natural philosophy of antiquity, according to the epistemological basis of which human emotions cannot always give him a clear idea of objective phenomena and processes.

As for inventions in medicine, the electrical equipment created by Nikola Tesla for medical research is widely distributed around the world. His experiments with high-voltage electric current (up to 2 million volts) led to his discovery of a method for cleaning contaminated surfaces. It has been found that by using electric current, it is possible to eliminate small rashes and pores on the skin and destroy microbes. This method is currently widely used in modern medicine. However,

Tesla "predicted" much earlier that high-frequency electric current could be applied to living organisms for the purpose of treatment, electric furnaces and electron microscopes would appear in the future. Tesla is also engaged in time engineering, an area that no one has touched before.

Methodology:

As we know, the essence of rationalism is revealed through the categories of cause and effect, essence and phenomenon, quantity and quality of philosophy. In epistemology, rationalism is widely regarded as the opposite of irrationalism, in the narrow sense of empiricism and sensationalism. Sources note that "thinking, which usually corresponds to perception and attitude to reality, becomes rational (based on reason, logic) and irrational (going beyond reason and logic, contradicting them or relying on botanical trust, non-Islamic, mystical factors)." The fundamental concepts of rationalism are thinking.

"Contemplation (Arabic. thinking, mental cognition) is a component of human spirituality. This is the mental stage of cognition, which determines the general, important characteristics of things and phenomena in the Universe, reflects the internal, necessary connections between them, new natural connections." Thinking has the following features: 1) in which reality is reflected in a generalized form. Unlike emotional cognition, contemplation allows us to focus our attention on its general reproducible characteristics and relationships, abstracting from imperfect, secondary (which are usually determined by the task facing cognition) signs of things and phenomena: 2) Contemplation indirectly reflects being. In it, new knowledge is generated by relying on existing knowledge, without referring directly to experience each time. Thinking is based on the connection between things and phenomena in this; 3) thinking consists of creative human activity, in which it becomes possible to study the most complex features of things and phenomena, anticipate phenomena, predict; 4) thinking exists in close contact with language, that is, thought is a spiritual phenomenon. It only realizes a material phenomenon, takes a form that other people can directly accept, feel, and becomes a means of mutual exchange of people's ideas.

Thinking is a mental activity, a set of conscious actions, the basis for cognition of the environment, social environment and being, an important condition for the rational effective organization of human activity. In the process of thinking, a person realizes the correctness, reliability and relation to being of what he sees, perceives, touches, imagines, and phenomena. Thinking is a set of views, concepts and hypotheses formed during the study of the mysteries of the Universe, through which a person learns how correct or incorrect conclusions and reasoning are.

"The thought process is inextricably linked not only with the human brain, but also with his heart and psyche. Depth, clarity, logic, independence, simplicity, creativity of human thought are the qualities of thinking."

Since time immemorial, scientific philosophers have recognized the rational aspect of intuition. The Greek philosopher Plato directly connects intuition with mental activity. He puts forward the idea that "thinking" is only the activity of one mind, it is free from emotional entanglement, it directly senses mental bodies."

"In the interpretation of philosophers of the 17th century, intuition alone does not give reliable knowledge, only intellectual intuition gives true knowledge." they felt. In particular, the French philosopher R. Descartes believes that "intuition is a solid expression of a thoughtful and mindful mind, logic and intuition have an inextricable connection." Descartes explores intuition in relation to one another, concluding that intuition is the supreme form of cognition.

B.Spinoza acknowledges rationalism in his views on cognition. He is mind-based, placing intellectual knowledge above the lower type of knowledge, that is, emotional knowledge. He recognized that direct observation of reality or intuition of reason is the highest type of intellectual knowledge. Spinoza declared clarity and fluency as a criterion of truth. G.V.Leibnis considers emotional cognition to be a sub-stage and sets the stage for mental cognition. It comes to the conclusion that only mental knowledge gives a complete picture of the commonality and necessity that exists in the world. In the opinion of Cante I, a person is not able to know the "thing in itself" (essence), he can only know the thing for us, that is, phenomena. As a result of the influence on our sensory organs" in the thing itself", a complex of sensations is formed. This complex is regulated by the power of our mind and is transformed into a whole. What we see as the laws of nature are in fact relationships introduced by reason into the world of phenomena. That is, according to Kant, our minds introduce laws into nature.

Irrationalism (Latin *irrationalis* - contrary to reason, zealous) is a philosophical trend that focuses on the non-contemplative aspects of human spiritual life, will, intuition, fantasy and similar concepts in the knowledge of the world, limiting or denying the possibilities of reason in the process of cognition."According to irrationalists, a person is not able to know all the secrets of objective reality with the help of reason, while reality is free from laws, subject to accidents, the blind will of the Curonians. It can be said that in acquiring new knowledge, not only logical thinking, its laws, methods and ways of forming concepts are of great importance, but also irrationality plays an important role in solving many scientific problems. As Liu de Broglie noted, "If the foundations of science were purely rational, irrational development and even, often, radical exchange would be impossible."He says that in the process of scientific research, not only rational, but also other individual features of a scientist's thinking are of great importance.

Conclusion. In our opinion, the unity, opposites of rational and irrational thinking are the cause, source of action and development. In the study of the essence and process of action of these concepts, it is necessary to distinguish between internal and external, fundamental and non-fundamental aspects, but there is also no absolute limit between them. In the process of cognition, they rot among themselves, switch to each other and have a different effect on thinking. Therefore, it is necessary to take into account a clear approach to each of the conflicts, the conditions in which the conflict is manifested, the environment, the situation. Intuition is a solid expression of this thoughtful and mindful mind. Logic and intuition have an inextricable connection. This opinion was expressed by A.We had also seen Bergson in his thoughts. Bergson evaluates logic and intuitiveness as special complementary means of knowledge and intelligence and intuition as forms of objective reality and cognition. Intuition is a socialized instinct that moves in the direction of creative evolution of life and understands its essence. Intelligence is action. In Fixte's eyes, intuition is an inner movement.

Lue de Broyle points out that if the foundations of science were purely rational, then development and even, often, radical exchange would not have occurred, he gave a high assessment of the place of irrational thinking. F.V.Schelling considered the connection of the object and the subject in the idea of absolute intelligence. It can be said that in the creative activity of the mind, the relationship of object and subject is harmonized. A.Schopengauer relates the concept of Will - will to mental activity. F.Nisshe associates the concept of intuition with morality. In this we can cite the following formula:

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